

THE CLOUD OF CONFLICT: IMPROVING EMOTIONAL REGULATION IN CHILDREN
THROUGH CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

by

Evelyn Berrum

ORCID ID: 0009-0000-8021-6802

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11479612

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2024

Approved by:

Dr. Sasha Zeedyk, Department of Child and Adolescent Studies

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

Date:

05/15/2024

5/24/2024

Abstract

Behavioral difficulties are a common characteristic of children's development. While there are many ways to help improve emotional regulation in children, reading books with themes of empathy and conflict resolution accomplishes this task and is widely accessible. *Isabel's Angry Cloud* is a fictional story of a seven-year-old-girl named Isabel who has a gray cloud that constantly hovers above her and struggles to control her temperament as a result. To support children's emotional development, this story incorporates figurative language to teach children empathy and handling emotional distress. Through an engaging storyline, vibrant illustrations, and relatable experiences, the book offers young readers the opportunity to explore emotion regulation strategies, particularly anger management. Young readers will reflect on how to banish their own, "angry cloud." Additionally, *Isabel's Angry Cloud* is a bilingual book written in English and Spanish. By promoting bilingualism, the story is accessible to readers from diverse backgrounds to support learning either/both languages. The bilingual format and guided questions also facilitate shared reading experiences between children and their caregivers.

Importance of Positive Emotion Regulation

A significant developmental milestone in children is the attainment of emotional literacy. Emotional literacy can be described as the ability to identify and manage one's feelings and emotions (Harper, 2016). This process begins in infancy and continuously develops throughout one's lifespan, and mastering these strategies is fundamental for adaptive functioning and conquering everyday challenges (Schoopmann et. al, 2023). For children, being able to successfully regulate one's own emotions has been shown to be a reliable predictor of academic competence (Harper, 2016). In a 21st century nationally representative United States sample, half of the kindergarten teachers surveyed said that half of their students or more were exhibiting school adjustment challenges (Rimm-Kaufmann, Pianta, & Cox, 2001). Correspondingly, the National Center of Education Statistics reported that students who displayed poor school adjustment were struggling to regulate their emotions (Lewit & Baker, 1995). Teachers explained that students with emotion regulation challenges are unable to communicate their thoughts, wants, and needs, and they are not enthusiastic about learning. Without positive school adjustment, students will not be able to have a sense of independence or feel capable and effective as learners. Students find compliance with school difficult because they struggle to pay attention in class, complete assignments, or inhibit impulsive behaviors. As a result, students with poor self regulation are at a higher risk of dropping out of school in the future (Blair & Diamond, 2008).

Children can effectively learn emotion regulation strategies through children's picture books (Schoopmann et. al, 2023). According to Bandura's social learning theory, children primarily acquire social behaviors through imitation (Bandura, 1971). According to Harper (2016), picture books featuring realistic scenarios and solutions with authentic characters offer

children models for navigating through their own emotions and conflicts. Illustrations of characters present facial expressions that aid readers into identifying and labeling human emotions. Children's literature also labels the emotions using appropriate words such as, "sad" and "happy." Acquiring this ability provides children the framework for using appropriate prosocial behaviors (Harper, 2016).

Shared Reading Outcomes

Encouraging literacy skills from an early age has a positive impact on children's literacy development. There are three common domains to early literacy skills: vocabulary, phonological awareness, and listening comprehension (Lacin, 2023) Mastering vocabulary (i.e., word knowledge and usage) is important as it indicates future performance in reading comprehension. Phonological awareness (i.e., the ability to recognize how letters represent sounds in words) foretells children's ability to decode words. Listening comprehension (i.e., the process of understanding spoken language), and it's crucial for language development (Lacin, 2023). Young children who demonstrate limited proficiency in these skills are likely to experience difficulties in reading and writing when they begin first grade. Studies have shown that obtaining these early literacy skills through shared reading is an effective strategy. Through shared reading children are more engaged and supported (Batista & Peruzzi, 2023). Through shared reading children are exposed to new learning opportunities because written language is different from the oral language parents use to have conversations with their children. Shared reading allows children to repeatedly be exposed to the words and context of the book, which taps into all three early literacy domains (i.e., vocabulary, phonics, and comprehension), resulting in an increase in their expressive and receptive vocabulary (Batista & Peruzzi, 2023). Furthermore, parents can scaffold their children's literacy skills through shared reading to promote the comprehension of new

information. To achieve this effectively, research suggests that parents read the text and pause to allow for thinking and engagement. When parents pause it gives children the opportunity to receive clarification, this method has shown an increase in phonological awareness compared to reading without interruption (Batista et. al, 2023).

Shared reading offers young readers undivided attention from their parents. It is a joint activity that results in earlier proximal process development. According to Bronfenbrenner, early proximal processes are important aspects of a child's development because they form the foundation of their psychological, biological, and social development (Bronfenbrenner, 1995). In addition, research suggests that parent-child shared reading promotes children's emotional skills, specifically empathy. Empathy is an important aspect of a child's development because it enables children to have appropriate emotional responses in social situations. Children can develop empathy and emotional understanding through their interactions in early childhood (Colwell, 2001). Shared reading is a type of interaction where children can learn about emotions by observing their parents' facial expression and tone of voice while reading to them. Furthermore, shared reading invites parents to have conversations pertaining to the characters emotions, reasons, motives, and intentions with their children. By doing so children may make connections with the characters and can adopt another's perspective without the emotional involvement required in real-life situations (Aram & Shapira, 2012).

Bilingualism In Children's Literature

A correlation between bilingualism in children and enhanced executive functioning (EF) has been consistently found in studies. Bilingual children have demonstrated advantages in working memory compared to monolingual children. Bilingual children outperform monolingual children in incongruent trials, where they are presented with a stimulus consisting of two

dimensions that require contradictory responses. These trials have shown that bilingual children process stimuli faster, can hold four ideas in their mind, and respond correctly to stimuli. Results suggest that bilingual children perform better at conflict resolution than monolingual children. Due to the fact that practicing two or more languages daily causes changes to one's cognitive performance. The cognitive change occurs due to the necessity of focusing on one language while having another language activated as well. A strong cognitive memory is crucial because it enables children to perform essential cognitive and academic tasks such as math, language, literacy, and numeracy achievement. For instance, in reading comprehension, children are required to retain previous texts in their mind and relate it to the current text. In numeracy achievement, children must retain numbers in their mind while applying new information to update their solution (Morales et. al, 2012).

Additionally, enhanced executive functioning effects appear to have long term effects on bilingual children. Compared to monolinguals, bilinguals experience delayed cognitive aging such as dementia by approximately 4 to 5 years. The delay in cognitive aging occurs because bilingualism strengthens one's adult neurogenesis, synaptogenesis, and functional connectivity. Adult neurogenesis, the process in which neurons are formed in the brain, is maintained at a higher level because of bilingualism demands. Bilingualism requires one to navigate various language systems such as semantics, syntax, grammar, and phonology. Synaptogenesis, the formation of new synapses is also maintained at a higher level. Bilingualism creates alternative brain networks to replace those that were previously damaged during cognitive aging. Functional activity, how two brain regions correlate with each other is strengthened in bilingualism because it involves attention shifting in two languages (Kim et. al, 2019).

Concept Development

Throughout this literature review, several studies were examined which emphasize the significance of children's literature in fostering cognitive and emotional development. One key aspect highlighted the role that children's books have in promoting emotional regulation. In creating *Isabel's Angry Cloud*, one of my primary aims is to provide children with emotion regulation strategies. For this purpose, I have created a storyline where the protagonist struggles with expressing her frustration and anger in an effective way. To achieve this, I created scenes where the protagonist attempts several commonly used emotion regulation techniques, such as taking deep breaths, counting to 10, and going on a walk. To further expand children's emotion regulation and vocabulary I have implemented words from an [emotion word list](#) created by Grosse and colleagues (2021). The word list includes words that are commonly used by children when they describe their emotions, and it is separated into age groups. I chose to implement words commonly used by the target age group of my book, which is ages 4 to 7 years old. Examples of these words include angry, happy, calm, and frustrated. The following sample page from the book shows this:

In addition, the literature review emphasizes the correlation between bilingualism in children and enhanced executive functioning. With this in mind, I have written my work in both languages, English and Spanish. By providing content in two languages, my objective is to strengthen a skill that enhances executive functioning such as, improved memory, conflict resolution abilities, and a delay in cognitive decline over time. Another intention is to reach a broader audience of young readers and their caregivers. For families where parents and children possess differing levels of language proficiency, "Isabel's Angry Cloud" serves to foster and safeguard the shared experience of reading together.

In addition a key aspect highlighted in the literature review is the correlation between parent-child shared reading and positive outcomes. To support these outcomes, I have implemented a reader's guide on page of *Isabel's Angry Cloud*. The reader's guide includes questions that make connections between the storyline and the reader's experiences. The purpose of the guide is to encourage parents to discuss the questions with their child to enhance story comprehension and themes.

Isabel's Angry Cloud Readers Guide

Questions are provided to make connections between the story and the young reader. Parents are encouraged to discuss the questions with their child to enhance story comprehension.

Guided questions:

- Which one of Pepe's relaxation tricks do you think will help you the next time you feel upset?
- Have you tried any of the tricks Pepe suggested?
- What other relaxation trick would you ask Isabel to practice?
- Can you think of a trusted friend to share your feelings to?
- Can you think of a time where you had your own angry cloud?
- What do you do when you're angry?

Storyline

The story revolves around a child named Isabel who learns a valuable lesson on the importance of regulating her emotions with the help of a friendly donkey. It begins with Isabel walking back home from school, upset about something that happened. Isabel soon realizes she's being followed home by a huge, gray cloud, symbolizing anger, raining on her and intensifying her distress. Unhappy with the cloud following her, Isabel tries unsuccessfully to dispel it, which only fuels her anger further. Later, Isabel encounters a town donkey named Pepe, who recognizes her temperament and suggests she practice some anger management techniques that have helped him in the past. Isabel then tries deep breathing exercises in an effort to make her angry cloud disappear and succeeds. With every breath she takes, she blows the cloud away, leaving her feeling calm and relieved that she's dispelled it.

Inspiration

As a Child and Adolescent Studies major with a minor in elementary school settings, I have accumulated experience working with children. Through internships and work placements in elementary school grades ranging from preschool to second grade, I've observed a common challenge for children: regulating their emotions, particularly anger. Many children resort to hitting their peers, shouting, or excessive crying when upset. Therefore, I aimed to create a book that addresses this issue through an engaging and interactive story. Additionally, the decision to produce my book in both English and Spanish was influenced by personal experience. My father's primary language is Spanish, with a limited working proficiency in English. As a result, my father was unable to provide me with academic support during my childhood. However, there was one bilingual book, "Un Gato y Un Perro" (A Cat and A Dog), that allowed him to support me in reading. This story was in English and Spanish, allowing my father to read me the story in Spanish and aiding in my acquisition of Spanish reading skills. This amusing and entertaining book also facilitated shared reading experiences between us and fostered a love for reading within me. With this in mind, in crafting my own story, I aimed to offer children who may also have parents with differing language fluency the same enriching experience.

Writing process

To develop my story, I visited my local library to draw inspiration from children's books, particularly focusing on bilingual, Hispanic culture and emotion management book titles. A list of these books are provided in the chart below.

Book	Author	Category
Palettero Man	Lucky Diaz	Hispanic Culture
Un Gato y Un Pero A Cat and a Dog	Claire Masurel	Bilingual Book

Isabel and her Colores Go to School	Alexandra Alessandri	Hispanic Culture
Grumpy Monkey	Suzanne Lang	Emotion regulation
I Am Stronger than Anger	Elizabeth Cole	Emotion regulation
Con Pollo	Jimmy Fallon Jeniffer Lopez	Bilingual Book

After gathering inspiration, I began drafting stories, initially considering two ideas: the chosen one and another where the protagonist is upset about her mother cooking something she dislikes. The theme of this alternative story would have emphasized gratitude for what one has. Opting for "Isabel's Angry Cloud," I began crafting the storyline. Influenced by Dr. Seuss books from my childhood, I decided to make my story rhyme, particularly in its beginning. To assist with rhyming, I utilized the website RhymeZone. Concurrently, I sought feedback from my mentor, Dr. Sasha Zeedyk. Dr. Zeedyk provided valuable guidance on the direction of my story and offered grammatical corrections and suggestions to ensure its suitability for preschool to first-grade students.

Illustration Process

Prior to my Honors project, my drawing skills were limited to basic pencil sketches, with no experience in digital art. However, I recognized that traditional pencil sketches would be more time consuming, therefore I decided to learn how to do digital art. To achieve this I utilized my Ipad and created illustrations through a drawing app called ProCreate. Below are a couple sketches I created during my illustration development.

Furthermore, my goal with the illustrations is to integrate Mexican culture, as the story is set in a town in Mexico. To accomplish this, I took photographs of the town in Mexico where my family is from to use as inspiration. For example, the character of the donkey Pepe was inspired by my grandfather's pet donkey.

Acknowledgements and Future work

I would like to express my gratitude to Dr. Sasha Zeedyk, not only is she an exceptional professor but she is also an amazing mentor. I am thankful for her unwavering support and generosity throughout this project. Her guidance and expertise have been invaluable at shaping the direction of my project. Without her encouragement and mentorship, developing this project

would not have been possible. Dr. Zeedyk's dedication to fostering academic excellence in her students is inspiring. I am very fortunate to have had Dr. Zeedyk as my mentor. I can not thank her enough. I would also like to thank CSUF Honors Program for offering this wonderful opportunity and encouraging students like myself to dive deeper into their passions.

As for future work, during the 2024 summer I intend to publish my book. I intend to learn more about the publishing process. However, before I began this process I would like to revisit some of my illustrations and most importantly the spanish dialogue of my book. I would like to ensure that the Spanish dialogue is correct and also rhymes to provide the same enjoyable experience the English dialogue does.

References

Bandura A. (1971). *Social Learning Theory*. General Learning Press

Batista Rocha, J. C., & da Mota, M. M. P. E. (2023). Does shared reading between parents and children affect the development of emerging literacy? *Trends in Psychology, 31*(2),

307–317. <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1007/s43076-021-00070-6>

Blair, C., & Diamond, A. (2008). Biological processes in prevention and intervention: the promotion of self-regulation as a means of preventing school failure. *Development and psychopathology*, 20(3), 899–911. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954579408000436>

Bronfenbrenner U. (1995). Developmental ecology through space and time: A future perspective. In Moen P., Elder G. H. J., Luscher K. (Eds.), *Examining lives in context: Perspectives on the ecology of human development*(pp. 619–647). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.

Colwell M.J. (2001): Mother-child emotion talk, mothers' expressiveness, and mother-child relationship quality: Links with children's emotional competence. *Dissertation Abstracts International: Section B: The Sciences and Engineering*, n. 61(7-B), p. 3877.

Denham, S. A., & Brown, C. (2010). “Plays nice with others”: Social–emotional learning and academic success. *Early Education and Development*, 21(5), 652-680.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2010.497450>

Harper, L. J. (2016). Preschool Through Primary Grades: Using Picture Books to Promote Social-Emotional Literacy. *YC Young Children*, 71(3), 80–86.

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/ycyoungchildren.71.3.80>

Laçin, E. (2023). A teacher-implemented shared-reading intervention to promote early literacy

skills of preschoolers and children in Turkey. *Reading Psychology*, 44(6), 589–603.

<https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1080/02702711.2023.2179142>

Lewit EM, Baker LS. School readiness. *The Future of Children*. 1995;5:128–139.

Morales, J., Calvo, A., & Bialystok, E. (2013). Working memory development in monolingual and bilingual children. *Journal of experimental child psychology*, 114(2), 187–202.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2012.09.002>

Parent-Child Shared Book Reading and Children’s Language, Literacy, and Empathy

Development1, www.researchgate.net/publication/311912621_Parent-Child_Shared_Book_Reading_and_Children’s_Language_Literacy_and_Empathy_Development1. Accessed 13 May 2024.

Rimm-Kaufman S, Pianta RC, Cox M. Teachers' judgments of problems in the transition to school. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*. 2001;15:147–166.

Schoppmann J, Severin F, Schneider S, Seehagen S. The effect of picture book reading on young children's use of an emotion regulation strategy. *PLoS One*. 2023 Aug 2;18(8):e0289403.

doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0289403. PMID: 37531357; PMCID: PMC10395841.

